

Climate-smart rewilding for Europe

Rewilding enablers and constraints in
rewilding cases

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Summary for Policymakers

Rewilding practice is subjected to many factors that enable and constrain the effectiveness and progress of rewilding. Drawing from the experience of eight (wildE) rewilding case studies across Europe from different countries and socioeconomic contexts the study identified sixteen enabling factors (“enablers”) and sixteen constraining factors (“constraints”) affecting rewilding practice. Results of a survey amongst case study leaders show that the strength of enablers and constraints changed from case study to case study. However, there was clear consensus across all case studies that the strength of enablers was larger than that of constraints, suggesting that factors facilitating the success and progress of rewilding practice are stronger than those obstructing it.

The survey also suggests that there is no single “silver bullet” for rewilding success in any given rewilding project, rather multiple enablers need to align to foster success collectively. We found that 11 of the 16 enablers identified were important across all case studies. In contrast, factors constraining rewilding were generally more idiosyncratic for every case study, suggesting that the obstacles to rewilding changes with socioecological/local context.

The study also evaluated which dimensions of rewilding were facilitated or constrained more frequently. A surprising result that emerged is that despite the heterogeneous and wide social, economic and ecological contexts represented by wildE case studies, many rewilding projects already put strong emphasis on devising measures that address the *Human dimensions* (*Social, Economic and Policy* aspects) to harness success and prevent failure. In addition, as would be logical, the *Natural dimensions* of rewilding also experience frequent enablers, by promoting the development of desirable *Ecological and Biophysical* features, and *Climate change adaptation* measures. However, the two wildE forestry case studies did not report strong provisions for *Climate change adaptation*, and *Climate change mitigation* was poorly accounted for (either positively or negatively) among all eight wildE case studies.

Overall, the study suggests that, despite prevailing views on the potential and the future of rewilding as a mainstream restoration practice are rather skeptical, rewilding projects across Europe experience many enablers, leverage the *Human dimensions* as much as the *Natural dimensions* of rewilding, and experience a much more reduced number of idiosyncratic constraints. Yet *Climate-smart* aspects need more attention in some instances, particularly *Climate-change mitigation*.

It is important to bear in mind that the survey builds on the expert judgement of case study leaders of which most are academics, who drew upon information gathered in local stakeholder workshops across eight case studies in different socioeconomic and cultural contexts, and, despite revealing some strong patterns and commonalities, both the stakeholders and the case studies are a subset that does not represent the whole range of rewilding intervention types. In addition, survey results must be taken with caution in respect to replication: the views of a case study might not fully represent the views of other similar case studies elsewhere.

Enablers	Constraints
(Regional) Land use trends Public co-benefits Natural disturbances Harvesting opportunities Congruence with policy Natural disasters Land ownership Willingness to experiment Area size and upscaling possibilities Leadership and management Initial investment costs Local community involvement and support Conflict mitigation strategies Cultural significance of the landscape Return of iconic species to the landscape [<i>Connectivity and state of nature in the surrounding landscape*</i>]	Natural disasters Natural disturbances Leadership and management Conflict with policy Human-wildlife conflicts Area size and upscaling possibilities Connectivity and state of nature in the surrounding landscape (Regional) Land use trends Return of iconic species to the landscape [<i>Land ownership</i>] [<i>Harvesting opportunities</i>] [<i>Aversion to experiment</i>] [<i>Local community exclusion or opposition</i>] [<i>Initial investment costs</i>] [<i>Cultural significance of the landscape</i>] [<i>Opportunity costs</i>]

Table of enablers and constraints across case studies and dimensions. Bold text = strong factors; Regular text = intermediate strength or idiosyncratic factors; Italics and brackets = weak factors.

Summary

Objectives

Rewilding practice is subjected to many factors that enable and constrain the effectiveness and progress of rewilding. However, the extent to which those factors are shared among different types of rewilding initiatives or rather are more idiosyncratic and context dependent is not well understood. In this report we build on the experience from the eight case studies in wildE to identify important enablers and constraints of rewilding, evaluate their relative strength and examine their impact across six different perspectives linked to the *Human* and *Natural* (including “Climate-smart”) dimensions of rewilding practice. These perspectives include i) *Social*; ii) *Economic*; iii) *Policy*; iv) *Ecological and Biophysical*; v) *Climate change mitigation*; vi) *Climate change adaptation* aspects of rewilding practice.

Methods and procedures

A first step involved a prospective survey among the eight wildE case studies, which allowed us to identify candidate enablers and constraints of rewilding practice. In a second step all case study leading teams answered independently a questionnaire to qualitatively assess the relative strength of every one of these enablers and constraints evaluated per every one of the six perspectives considered in every case study. Subsequently, the results of the questionnaire focused on quantifying the scores and ranking of enablers and constraints per case study, across case studies, per perspective and across perspectives. This allowed us to compare enablers and constraints of rewilding across a wide European gradient of social, economic, political and environmental contexts, and evaluate their impact on the *Human* and *Natural* dimensions of rewilding and *Climate-smart* perspectives.

Main Results

We identified sixteen enablers and constraints affecting rewilding practice. There was a high level of heterogeneity amongst case studies and within case studies in the strength of enablers and constraints. Some case studies experience multiple strong enablers, some others only a few strong enablers, and some others consistently weak enablers. However, and perhaps surprisingly, factors enabling rewilding are stronger than those constraining rewilding across case studies, per case study, across perspectives and per perspective, suggesting that factors facilitating rewilding practice are stronger than those preventing it. Furthermore, no “silver-bullet” was found across these enablers, as multiple factors contributed to facilitate rewilding (11 of the 16 enablers considered have wide leverage across case studies and perspectives), suggesting that rewilding is currently supported by addressing multiple fronts.

In contrast, factors constraining rewilding were generally idiosyncratic of every case study, and few case studies showed several consistent constraints. There were three groups of relatively important constraints. Firstly, results suggest that risks related to natural events like fire, floods, droughts, windstorms and pest outbreaks might represent a burden in rewilding projects. Secondly, case studies report that leadership and aspects related to management of rewilded areas, the conflicts that rewilding might generate with policy, the problems generated by wildlife conflicts, and in some cases, the return of iconic species can slow down

rewilding progress. Thirdly, the limitations posed by the size of the rewilding area and the landscape surrounding the case studies, the dominant regional land uses and state of nature and connectivity with other natural areas might constrain rewilding practice and success. Thus, focal attention to minimizing these constraints could be instrumental in facilitating success and progress in a wide range of rewilding interventions. Another key inference from the results is that some constraints that are commonly assumed to have a negative impact on rewilding show weak leverage or are idiosyncratic to some specific case studies. These include *Land ownership*, *Harvesting opportunities*, *Aversion to experiment*, *Local community exclusion or opposition*, *Initial investment costs*, *Cultural significance of the landscape* and *Opportunity costs*. Some of these factors are commonly assumed to pose substantial barriers to rewilding, yet our survey strongly suggests otherwise. In addition, another surprising result from our survey is the realization that the *Human dimensions* of rewilding (*Social*, *Economic* and *Policy* perspectives) are much more enabled than constrained, highlighting that, despite the heterogeneous and wide social, economic and ecological contexts represented by wildE case studies, rewilding projects already put generally strong emphasis in the *Human dimensions*. Results also show that the *Natural* dimensions of rewilding, including *Ecological and Biophysical*, and *Climate change adaptation* perspectives, also experience frequent enablers (except in the two case studies involving commercial forestry partners where *Climate change adaptation* appears poorly addressed). On the contrary, *Climate change mitigation* is poorly enabled or constrained in rewilding projects. This highlights that *Climate-smart* aspects are heterogeneously addressed in rewilding practice: while measures aligning with *Climate change adaptation* are already being implemented in most case studies at some extent (excluding forestry plantations), *Climate change mitigation* (by e.g. capturing carbon and/or reducing greenhouse gas emissions) has received less attention in rewilding practice.

In a nutshell, our study suggests that despite prevailing views on the potential and the future of rewilding as a mainstream *Climate-smart* restoration practice are rather skeptical, rewilding projects across Europe experience many enablers, leverage the *Human* dimensions as much as the *Natural* dimensions of rewilding, and experience a much more reduced number of idiosyncratic constraints. These results picture an encouraging moment for the progress and success of *Climate-smart* rewilding practice.

Authors/Teams involved: lead by Nacho Villar (KNAW) and Liesbeth Bakker (KNAW), in collaboration with Joana Santana (BIOPOLIS) and Pedro Beja (BIOPOLIS). All wildE case study leading teams contributed to the questionnaire.

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1. Introduction

The deliverable D2.1 “*Rewilding enablers and constraints in rewilding cases*” is part of the Work Package 2 (WP2) “*Rewilding practice*”. The objective of WP2 is to develop evidence-based guidelines for implementing multi-objective, cost-effective Climate-smart rewilding practices, based on case-comparative methods applied across a diverse set of socio-environmental contexts. Within this remit, this report seeks to identify factors that enable and constrain rewilding practice. Rewilding interventions experience factors and circumstances that impose hurdles on the progress and success of rewilding, and some others that facilitate rewilding. Some of these factors can be idiosyncratic and linked to the specific context of a rewilding site, and some others might be more general and shared among many rewilding sites. However, so far there has been no attempt to compile factors that enable and/or constrain rewilding following a structured and comparative method. However, identification of general factors that may positively and negatively affect rewilding practice in a systemic manner is allegedly a pre-requisite to maximize the success in the planning and implementation of rewilding.

The eight wildE case studies represent a sort of “rewilding diaspora” of different types of rewilding interventions spanning across seven European countries and a wide range of social, economic, political and environmental contexts, and include both public and private ventures. This provides a unique opportunity to identify important enablers and constraints that might influence rewilding practice across wide gradients. To achieve this goal, during the second half of 2025 we put in motion a two-step “bottom-up” approach to identify important enablers and constraints of rewilding and evaluate their relative strength. The first step involved a prospective survey among the eight wildE case studies, which allowed us to identify candidate enablers and constraints of rewilding practice. In the second step all case study leading teams answered independently an online questionnaire (see *Questionnaire 1. Enablers (supplementary file)* and *Questionnaire 2. Constraints (supplementary file)*) that allowed the qualitative assessment of the relative strength of every one of these enablers and constraints.

In addition, the questionnaire was designed to allow the examination of the impact of every enabler and every constraint on every one of six different perspectives linked to the *Human* and *Natural* dimensions of rewilding practice. The perspectives considered are i) social; ii) economic; iii) policy; iv) ecological and biophysical; v) climate change mitigation; vi) climate change adaptation aspects of rewilding practice. The latter two perspectives specifically address the *Climate-smart* aspects of rewilding, which is a rooting element of the wildE project. This not only allows us to examine how different factors affect the different perspectives considered, but also to leverage which of these perspectives are more strongly enabled or constrained per case study and across case studies. For example, a widespread intuitive conception is that rewilding pays more attention to ecological outcomes than to socioeconomic aspects. The approach followed in the questionnaire allows us to test if this is the case building on the experience of these eight case studies across Europe.

The questionnaire measured the relative strength of each enabler and constraint on a qualitative scale, ranging from 0 (no effect) to 3 (strong enabler or strong constraint). When a particular enabler did not apply to a specific perspective in a given case study, a N.A. (not applicable) answer was coded. The analyses of the results were focused on quantifying the median scores and ranking the enablers and constraints per case study, across case studies, per perspective, across perspectives and across case studies and perspectives. This allowed us to compare enablers and constraints of rewilding across a wide European gradient of social, economic, political and environmental contexts, and evaluate their impact on the *Human* and *Natural* dimensions of rewilding and *Climate-smart* perspectives.

2. Results

2.1 Candidate enablers and constraints

Sixteen candidate enablers and sixteen aligned constraints of rewilding practice in the case studies were identified through the prospective survey among the eight wildE case studies (*Table 1*). Every one of these sixteen enablers and constraints affected at least one case study. The alignment of enablers and constraints allowed us to enquire whether, in a particular case study, some elements of a specific factor could act as enablers and some others as constraints of rewilding. For example, small area in a rewilding project might facilitate implementation of some rewilding practices in some instances due to reduced costs and cost-effective management involved, but also simultaneously constrain the implementation of rewilding practices due to insufficient area for trophic rewilding with large-sized species. Some examples of each enabler and constraint follows.

Enablers	Constraints
Natural disasters	Natural disasters
Natural disturbances	Natural disturbances
Local community involvement and support	Local community exclusion or opposition
Leadership and management	Leadership and management
Willingness to experiment	Aversion to experiment
Cultural significance of the landscape	Cultural significance of the landscape
Land ownership	Land ownership
(Regional) Land use trends	(Regional) Land use trends
Connectivity and state of nature in the surrounding landscape	Connectivity and state of nature in the surrounding landscape
Area size and upscaling possibilities	Area size and upscaling possibilities
Congruence with policy	Conflict with policy
Conflict mitigation strategies	Human-wildlife conflicts
Return of iconic species to the landscape	Return of iconic species to the landscape
Harvesting opportunities	Harvesting opportunities
Initial investment costs	Initial investment costs
Public co-benefits	Opportunity costs

Table 1. List of all candidate enablers and constraints that emerged from the prospective survey among the eight wildE case studies.

Enablers

Natural disasters

Sometimes an event can demonstrate that current practices are failing, giving urgency and need for new avenues. For example, after major natural disasters, such as catastrophic flooding, windstorms, or dramatic wildfires, or societal disasters, such as economic collapse or covid, public awareness might lead to look for management alternatives that align with rewilding.

Natural disturbances

Natural disturbances may contribute to e.g. increasing landscape resilience and support climate change mitigation, and in some cases, this may lead to alleviating the economic impact of climate change. For example, in floodplains, allowing room for the river allows preventing increasing drought and flooding episodes brought about by climate change, and their ecological and economic impacts.

Local community involvement and support

Involving local communities to co-develop a rewilding area may benefit rewilding opportunities. For example, locals may become keen on the prospects of local tourism business opportunities derived from rewilding, or be involved in the co-creation and vision of the rewilding project from early stages.

Leadership and management

Presence of visionary groups that initiate new thinking on old problems can create a positive momentum for rewilding. For example, strong leadership may foster moving from species conservation to ecosystem restoration to protect species or combining harvesting with nature conservation.

Willingness to experiment

Openness to trying new forms of nature conservation and restoration or landscape management. For example, when organizations or people are willing to try out leaving dead wood in the forest or letting small fires burn to prevent large fires, this may provide opportunities for rewilding.

Cultural significance of the landscape

A landscape with low specific cultural values attached to it may be easier to rewild. For example, formerly large-scale intensively used agricultural lands with limited cultural values can be easier to rewild than small-scale farming fields with hedgerows.

Land ownership

When the ownership of a potential rewilding area is concentrated in a few owners (either public, private or communal) it may be easier to agree on landscape scale interventions.

(Regional) Land use trends

Regional trends in land use may contribute to providing opportunities for successful rewilding. For example, abandonment of agricultural or industrial use at regional scales may increase the available land for rewilding interventions when there are few other competing land uses.

Connectivity and state of nature in the surrounding landscape

The surrounding landscape may favor rewilding progress. For example, heterogenous landscapes or those close/connected to nature reserves are more favorable to harbor high biodiversity, and riverine areas can be relatively well connected to distant areas by the river.

Area size and upscaling possibilities

When local rewilding can be upscaled then this may favor this form of rewilding and its local implementation. For example, when local re-introduction of wildlife can contribute towards growth to a larger regional

population, such as beavers along rivers, or when a site is part of a regional network of nature reserves, or Natura 2000, then this may help implementation.

Congruence with policy

(National) policies may create opportunities for rewilding or restrict the opportunities. For example, flood risk reduction programs may favor rewilding of floodplains, and national/regional restoration targets may provide incentives for rewilding forest plantations or abandoned agricultural land.

Conflict mitigation strategies

There may be strategies in place to avoid/minimize conflict emerging from rewilding, or adequately manage it. For example, in rewilding areas with recreation and public access, signaling paths, putting up fences and/or surveillance may limit the risk of interaction with protected and/or potentially dangerous wildlife while allowing public recreation. Likewise, there may be subsidies for dealing with livestock attacks by wolves which may help to reduce losses.

Return of iconic species to the landscape

The return of iconic species to the landscape may help the implementation and progress of rewilding. For example, the return of the wolf, bear, European bison, Eurasian beaver, Golden Eagle or vultures may inspire positive attitudes towards rewilding by those who see this as an opportunity for increasing economic income from wildlife tourism. Also, this may help to receive public support from people living in other regions.

Harvesting opportunities

Rewilding can sometimes benefit from win-win scenarios by which natural resource use can be combined with benefits for nature (and people). For example, wood harvesting, clay mining and even wildlife harvesting (e.g. “wild meat”) can be managed in a way that aligns with rewilding principles, whilst providing income and contributing to climate change mitigation or/and adaptation.

Initial investment costs

When initial investment is low, then it is easier to implement rewilding actions started. For example starting small or when the land is not so expensive this enables rewilding. Also, if subsidies or funding from NGOs are available these may also help to get started.

Public co-benefits

Increasing natural values delivers benefits for people beyond directly involved stakeholders. For example, rewilding may provide increased recreational opportunities, business opportunities linked to rewilding in the area, increased land and/or house prices, reduced fire mitigation costs resulting from vegetation fuel reduction by large (semi)wild herbivores, reduced flooding or/and drought risk or by limiting the impact of pest outbreaks.

Constraints

Natural disasters

After major natural disasters, public infrastructure or management may place a strong focus on avoiding further disasters, especially in densely populated areas. For example, after major flooding in Mediterranean regions,

the flow of rivers may be redirected away from major cities through major infrastructure projects, or after a major dramatic wildfire, land use management may be directed to prevent any minor or major fire.

Natural disturbances

Natural disturbances may be seen as a nuance and an obstacle in conventional management practices and therefore their use as a rewilding tool, to increase landscape resilience and support climate change mitigation may be controversial and/or neglected. For example, windstorms and pest outbreaks may be perceived by foresters as a hazard to avoid. Also, when a region is prone to natural hazards (like drought or wildfires) this may constrain the willingness to implement rewilding. For example, private companies in the Mediterranean region may not want to assume a rewilding approach because they are too concerned with fire risk.

Local community exclusion or opposition

Local community involvement may ultimately result in reduced rewilding opportunities if other practices are preferred. Also, local community involvement may be poor in the co-creation of the rewilding vision, leading to an impression of “imposed rewilding”, e.g. by policies and agreements at the regional or national level.

Leadership and management

The absence of visionary groups that initiate new thinking on old problems can hamper a positive momentum for rewilding, and perpetuate the “status-quo”, inaction or repeat old solutions to old problems. Furthermore, it is even conceivable that there is strong opposition by charismatic/influential leaders against rewilding.

Aversion to experiment

Risk aversion to trying new forms of nature conservation and restoration or landscape management. Or, alternatively, when there is a strong conservative culture in for instance state forestry or administrative departments then this may reduce rewilding opportunities.

Cultural significance of the landscape

When the landscape has high cultural value, then this may constrain rewilding implementation. For example, the cultural significance of former extensive pastoral areas and traditional small-scale farming Mediterranean mosaic landscapes, or cultural riverine landscapes, may make them more difficult to rewild in some instances.

Land ownership

Land ownership may be a barrier for rewilding in some circumstances, for example when the land ownership is scattered across many (types of) landowners, or when it belongs to multiple public administrations at different levels, agreeing on landscape scale interventions may be difficult.

(Regional) Land use trends

Regional trends in land use may constrain opportunities for successful rewilding, for example when the land is used for increasingly intensive agriculture or increasing urban developments, forestry monocultures, or solar panel fields.

Connectivity and state of nature in the surrounding landscape

The surrounding landscape may slow down rewilding progress. For example, isolated nature areas amid intense agriculture have less potential than well connected areas to harbor high biodiversity which can colonize adjacent areas under rewilding.

Area size and upscaling possibilities

When upscaling possibilities are lacking then this may limit both the local rewilding actions and its application elsewhere. For example, when animals remain contained in a small area, such as European bison in a fenced area with no sight on expansion, then this may not favor implementation.

Conflict with policy

(National) policies may create opportunities for rewilding or restrict the opportunities. For example, sanitary and animal welfare policies may prohibit treating European bison or semi-domestic large herbivore breeds as wild animals reducing rewilding possibilities.

Human-wildlife conflicts

Rewilding may lead to human-wildlife conflicts in some circumstances. For example, strict protection in a rewilding area may curtail recreation and public access, or the arrival/reintroduction of wildlife like deer, geese or carnivores may generate conflicts with foresters, farmers and livestock breeders, respectively.

Return of iconic species to the landscape

The return of iconic species to the landscape may curtail the implementation and progress of rewilding, for example, if local landowners and land managers perceive that the protection status of these species may legally constrain their economic activities and complicate their management or logistics, or there are strong political views against the return of such iconic animals.

Harvesting opportunities

In some circumstances elements of rewilding may clash against traditional models of resource use, such as intensive management in forestry plantations, livestock grazing, fodder harvesting or agricultural plantations, and even electricity harvesting from e.g. solar panel fields or windmills. In such circumstances managers or landowners may be reluctant to embrace rewilding.

Initial investment costs

When initial costs are high then this may constrain rewilding actions. For example, when initiatives have to buy land that is very expensive, or subsidies or funding from foundations or NGOs are lacking, this can constrain rewilding.

Opportunity costs

Rewilding can compete against a myriad of other land uses and lead to opportunity costs by losing the prospect of generating income from those uses. In some areas such opportunity costs may be more acute than in others.

2.2 Enablers and constraints of rewilding in case studies

The results from the qualitative survey showed that there is large heterogeneity in the enablers and constraints of rewilding within every case study and among different case studies (*Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3*) and

that some case studies reported overall stronger enablers and/or constraints than others (Figure 1). *Tatras* was the case study that reported the stronger overall effect of enablers (median score of enablers= 2), followed by *Barcelona Metropolitan*, *Baixo Sabor* and *Gelderse Poort* (all with median = 2); *Antarr* and the *Ruhrgebiet* were in a second group with moderate positive effect of enablers in the success of rewilding (median = 1), while *Coillte* and *Sveaskog* -where rewilding was enabled with the least strength– reported generally lower scores of enablers (median = 0). For constraints of rewilding, *Tatras* also scored the highest overall (median score = 1), followed by *Coillte* (median = 0) and the rest of case studies (all with median = 0).

Figure 1. Overall strength of enablers (left panel) and constraints (right panel) in all case studies.

Boxplots show, per case study, the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points).

Examination of scores and ranks suggested that the importance of every enabler and constraint changed per case study (see Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrating enablers and constraints ranked in every case study, and also Table A1 and Table A2 in the Annexes for scores per case study). This suggests that no enabler nor constraint of rewilding could be identified as a universally strongest one across case studies. Yet, as illustrated in Table 2, a number of factors had a strong influence on enabling rewilding across several case studies: 13 enablers had high score (=score equal or higher than 2) in more than 2 case studies, and 5 of them had a high score in at least half of the case studies (see Table 2). Likewise, there were a number of factors that had a strong influence on constraining rewilding across several case studies. However, the scores of these constraining factors were generally lower than those of enablers, suggesting that rewilding experiences more enablers than constraints across wildE case studies: 8 constraints had moderate score (=score higher than 0 but lower than 2) but only 6 had high score in more than 2 case studies; and only 2 of them had a high score in at least half of the case studies (see Table 2). A subset of 12 top enablers had aspects that resulted in them operating also as top constraints (albeit again the scores of these constraints were generally lower - hence the strength weaker- than those of enablers, see Table 2, Table A1 and Table A2 for more details).

Figure 2. Strength of all enablers in every case study.

Enablers are ordered, per case study, from larger to lesser strength (top to bottom). Boxplots show the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points) per enabler. Enablers and constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

Figure 3. Strength of all constraints in every case study.

Constraints are ordered, per case study, from larger to lesser strength (top to bottom). Boxplots show the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points) per constraint. Enablers and constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

Case study	Top enablers	Top constraints	Top simultaneously
Across case studies	Regional land use (6) Public cobenefits (5) Natural disturbances (4) Harvesting oport (4) Congruence policy (4) Natural disasters (3) Land ownership (3) Willing experiment (3) Area and upscaling (3) Conflict mitigation (3) Leadership management (2) Initial costs (2) Cultural landscape (2)	Natural disasters (4) Regional land use (3) Aversion experiment (2) Return iconic spp (3) Land ownership (4) Wildlife conflicts (4) Leadership management (3) Conflict policy (3) Natural disturbances (2) Local community (3) Area and upscaling (3) Initial costs (2) Harvesting opportunities (2) Nature connect around (2)	Regional land use Public cobenefits Natural disturbances Harvesting oport Congruence/conflict policy Natural disasters Land ownership Willing/aversion experiment Area and upscaling Conflict mitigation/wildlife conflicts Leadership management Initial costs
Tatras	Natural disturbances Initial costs Natural disasters Regional land use Area and upscaling	Natural disasters Regional land use Aversion experiment Return iconic spp Land ownership Wildlife conflicts	Natural disasters Regional land use
Barcelona Metropolitan	Harvesting oport Congruence policy Conflict mitig Regional land use Public cobenefits	Leadership management Natural disasters Land ownership	None
Baixo Sabor	Public co-benefits Initial costs Regional land use Harvesting oport Conflict mitigation	Wildlife conflicts Conflict policy Natural disturbances Local community	Conflict mitigation/Wildlife conflict
Gelderse Poort	Natural disturbances Natural disasters Leadership management Harvesting oport Congruence policy	Return of iconic sp Conflict policy Land ownership Area and upscaling Regional land use	Congruence policy/Conflict policy
Antarr	Land ownership Public co-benefits Congruence with policy Willing experiment Regional land use	Natural disasters Initial costs Harvesting oport Wildlife conflicts	None
Ruhrgebiet	Regional land use Land ownership	Nature connect around Area and upscaling	None

	Willing experiment Cultural landscape Public cobenefits	Local community Leadership management	
Coillte	All enablers	Many constraints (see Fig. 3)	All
Sveaskog	Natural disturbances Harvesting oport Area and upscaling Public cobenefits Area and upscaling	All constraints	None

Table 2. Top enablers and constraints per case study.

The table shows the top five enablers and constraints for every case study, with strong enablers and strong constraints (median 2 or higher) highlighted in purple bold and red bold text, respectively; moderate enablers or constraints (median between 0 and 2) in regular text; and weak enablers and constraints (median score of 0) in brown bold text. For every case study, the last column shows factors that qualify as strong enablers and strong constraints simultaneously. The first row of the table lists enablers and constraints that appear in more than one case study, with the number of case studies in which it occurs in brackets. Enablers and constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

In addition, all case studies had some enablers with aspects that resulted in them operating also as constraints of rewilding (see Table 3). *Natural disturbances*, *Leadership management*, *the state and connectivity of Nature around the rewilded area*, its *Area and opportunities for upscaling* and *Harvesting opportunities* had aspects that resulted in enabling and constraining rewilding simultaneously in 5 case studies (though with different strength). All other factors acted as both enablers and constraints in 4 or less case studies simultaneously (see Table 3 for details).

Enabler	Constraint	Antarr	Coillte	Ruhrgebiet	Sveaskog	Baixo Sabor	Barcelona Metropolitan	Gelderse Poort	Tatras	Nr case studies both
Natural disturbances	Natural disturbances	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	5
Leadership management	Leadership management	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	5
Nature connect around	Nature connect around	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	5
Area and upscaling	Area and upscaling	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	5
Harvesting oport	Harvesting oport	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	5
Natural disasters	Natural disasters	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	4
Local community	Local community	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	4
Land ownership	Land ownership	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	4
Congruence policy	Conflict policy	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	4
Region land use	Region land use	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	3
Conflict mitig	Wildlife conflicts	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	3
Return iconic sp	Return iconic sp	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	3
Initial costs	Initial costs	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	3
Public cobenefits	Opp costs	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	3
Willing experiment	Aversion experiment	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
Cultural landscape	Cultural landscape	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2

Table 3. Factors operating as enablers and constraints simultaneously per case study.

Highlighted in pink and score =1 indicates that this factor was identified as both enabler and constraint (aligned in the first and second column), irrespective of the strength. Enablers and constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

A complementary insight can be gained by applying a standard hierarchical clustering algorithm to the data for case studies, enablers and constraints (Figure 4). For enablers, the case studies *Barcelona Metropolitan*, *Gelderse Poort*, *Tatras* and *Baixo Sabor* cluster together: these case studies showed the largest overall effects of enablers on rewilding (all with median scores of 2, see Figure 1), and also share the common feature of

having very few moderate or weak enablers (Figure 2 and Figure 4). The rest of case studies, where weaker effects of enablers were reported, form another cluster that contains two subclusters: a first one with overall intermediate strength of enablers (median scores of 1, see Figure 1) and with about half of enablers with moderate or weak strength (Figure 2), containing the cases *Antarr* and *Ruhrgebiet*; and a second one with overall very low strength of enablers (median scores of 0, see Figure 1) and a majority of enablers with little strength, containing the cases *Coillte* and *Sveaskog*. However, an equivalent clustering exercise for constraints and case studies returns a much less structured picture (Figure 4), where case studies with strongest and second strongest effects of constraints in rewilding (*Tatras* - median score of 1 - and *Coillte* - median score of 0 -, respectively) do not cluster together, and other case studies show scattered clustering. These results suggest that, despite the high level of heterogeneity, many factors add up to the success of rewilding in cases where rewilding is strongly enabled (*Barcelona Metropolitan*, *Gelderse Poort*, *Tatras* and *Baixo Sabor*), whilst for case studies with weak overall strength of enablers (*Coillte* and *Sveaskog*), factors aligned with rewilding are also consistently weaker. An intermediate group consists of case studies where rewilding is moderately enabled (*Antarr* and *Ruhrgebiet*), where circa half of enabling factors are strong and another half are weak. Interestingly, many of these strong enabling factors are shared between these two case studies, including: *Regional land use*, *Land ownership*, *Public cobenefits*, *Congruence with policy*, *Willingness to experiment*, *Cultural landscape* and *Area and upscaling*. Results also suggest that these “grouping categories” are absent for constraints, which show a lesser impact on rewilding than enablers (lower scores across and per case study, see Figure 1, but consider also results reported across previous paragraphs), display more heterogeneous patterns, and where constraints seem more idiosyncratic to particularities of each specific case study.

Figure 4. Clustering of case studies according to enablers (left panel) and constraints (right panel).

The intensity of the color illustrates the strength (=median score) for every factor and case study combination. The vertical dendrogram on top shows hierarchical clustering relationships between case studies, while the horizontal shows clustering relations between factors. Three case study clusters emerged when considering the strength of enablers (highlighted with boxes: a cluster with strong enablers (“Strong”), a cluster with few strong enablers (“Medium”), and a cluster with no strong enablers (“Weak”). No obvious clusters were found for constraints, where only two case studies experienced weak to moderate constraints (highlighted with boxes). Enablers and constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

Key take home messages from section 2.2

- There is a high level of heterogeneity amongst case studies and within case studies in the strength of enablers and constraints.
- Surprisingly, factors enabling rewilding are stronger than those constraining rewilding across case studies and per case study.
- Some case studies experience multiple strong enablers (*Barcelona Metropolitan, Gelderse poort, Tatra and Baixo sabor*), some others some strong (and shared) enablers (*Antarr and Ruhrgebiet*), and some others consistently weak enablers (*Coillte and Sveaskog*).
- No “omnibus” enabler was found: many enablers add up in case studies where rewilding is enabled with more strength, such as *Barcelona Metropolitan, Gelderse poort, Tatra and Baixo sabor*.
- In addition, constraints are, in contrast to enablers, more idiosyncratic of every case study. *Tatra* and *Coillte* where the case studies with higher (yet generally moderate to weak) constraints scores.
- All case studies had some enablers with aspects that resulted in them operating also as constraints of rewilding.

2.3 Enablers and constraints of different perspectives

Another part of analyses focuses in which perspectives are mostly enabled and constrained across case studies. Results from these analyses suggest that the *Social* and *Ecological and Biophysical* perspectives are the most enabled (median score across case studies = 2, *Figure 5*), followed by the *Economic, Climate change adaptation* and *Policy* perspectives (median = 1). *Climate change mitigation* is the least enabled perspective, with a median score of 0, and only strongly enabled by the factors *Willingness to experiment* and *Regional land use* (*Table 4* and also *Figure A3* in Annexes).

Scores for constraints in perspectives were lower than for enablers, with all perspectives showing a median score of 0 across case studies (*Figure 5*), suggesting that there are few and generally weak factors constraining the different dimensions of rewilding. The *Economic*, the *Ecological and Biophysical* perspective, and the *Social* and *Policy* perspectives were constrained at some extent in some case studies, but except for *Coillte* and *Sveaskog*, these perspectives were much more enabled than constrained in almost the totality of the rest of case studies (see *Figure A1* and *Figure A2* in Annexes). An exception is *Tatra*, where both the *Economic* and *Social* perspectives experienced simultaneously strong enablers and constraints. Both the *Climate change mitigation* and *Climate change adaptation* perspectives in rewilding suffered from minor constraints in general but also in every one of the case studies individually (*Figure 5* and also *Figure A2* in Annexes).

Figure 5. Overall strength of enablers (left panel) and constraints (right panel) per perspective.

Boxplots show, per perspective, the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points).

Examining the specific enablers and constraints for every perspective independently suggests again that factors enabling rewilding have overall stronger weights than factors constraining rewilding across case studies. Many of the perspectives shared strong enablers, resulting in a specific set of eight strong enablers across perspectives (Table 4): *Public cobenefits* was the strongest enabler across perspectives (5 out of 6 perspectives), followed by *Regional land use* and *Willingness to experiment* (both strongly enabling 5 out of 6 perspectives). *Leadership and management*, *Land ownership* and *Congruence with policy* were also very relevant across half of the perspectives considered, while *Harvesting opportunities* and *Natural disturbances* were crucial enablers of 2 of the 6 perspectives considered.

There were no strong constraints in any of the perspectives or across perspectives; however, *Leadership and management*, *Conflict with policy* and *Area and upscaling* had weak to moderate leverage across half or less than half of the perspectives considered (Table 4). Additionally, there was also a very limited set of factors that could act simultaneously as enablers and constraints of one perspective (Table 4): *Local community* (Social perspective); *Leadership and management*, *Area and upscaling*, and *Regional land use* (Ecological and biophysical perspective); *Harvesting opportunities* (Economic perspective); *Congruence/Conflicts with policy* and *Leadership and management* (Policy perspective). Of these, only *Congruence/Conflicts with policy* and *Leadership and management* consistently operated as relevant simultaneous enablers and constraints across perspectives. Neither *Climate change adaptation* nor *Climate change mitigation* experienced factors that acted as simultaneously as enablers and constraints (Table 4), and the *Climate change mitigation* perspective experienced generally weak enablers and even weaker constraints.

In addition, the *Return of iconic species*, *Nature and connectivity* around the rewilded area, *Conflict mitigation*, and aspects linked to the *Cultural landscape* showed lesser positive (as enablers) or negative (as constraints) leverage across perspectives than other factors, suggesting that these factors have very limited leverage in enabling or constraining rewilding across multiple dimensions (Table 4). Collectively, these results suggest that from a “perspective” approach, the enablers and constraints of rewilding are far more identifiable than on a “case-per-case study” basis.

Perspective	Top enablers	Top constraints	Top simultaneously
Across perspectives	Public cobenefits (5) Regional land use (4) Willing experiment (4) Leadership management (3)	None strong Leadership management (3) Conflict policy (3) Area and upscaling (2)	Leadership management Congruence/conflict policy

	Land ownership (3) Congruence policy (3) Harvesting opport (2) Natural disturbances (2)		
Social	Local community Public cobenefits Conflict mitig Land ownership Harvesting opport	Leadership management Local community Conflict policy Return iconic sp Cultural landscape Natural disasters	Local community
Ecological and biophysical	Leadership management Natural disturbances Area and upscaling Willing experiment Regional land use	Nature connect around Wildlife conflicts Regional land use Leadership management Area and upscaling	Leadership management Area and upscaling Regional land use
Economic	Harvesting opport Willing experiment Public cobenefits Regional land use Initial costs	Harvesting opport Natural disturbances Conflict policy Area and upscaling Initial costs	Harvesting opport
Climate change adaptation	Natural disturbances Public cobenefits Willing experiment Leadership management Congruence policy	Natural disasters Regional land use Land ownership Leadership management Area and upscaling	None
Policy	Regional land use Congruence policy Public cobenefits Leadership management Land ownership	Conflict policy Leadership management Wildlife conflicts Land ownership	Congruence policy/Conflict policy Leadership management
Climate change mitigation	Willing experiment Region land use Land ownership Public cobenefits Congruence policy	Natural disasters Nature connect around Regional land use Natural disturbances	None

Table 4. Top enablers and constraints per perspective.

The table shows the top five enablers and constraints for every perspective, with strong enablers and strong constraints (median 2 or higher) highlighted in purple bold and red bold text, respectively; moderate enablers or constraints (median between 0 and 2) in regular text; and weak enablers and constraints (median score of 0) in brown bold text. For every perspective, the last column shows factors that qualify as strong enablers and strong constraints simultaneously. The first row of the table lists enablers and constraints that appear in more than one perspective, with the number of perspectives in which it occurs in brackets. Enablers and constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

Applying a standard hierarchical clustering algorithm to the data for case studies and perspectives, reveals that, similarly to Section 2.2, the case studies *Sveaskog* and *Coillte* form a cluster where all perspectives are low to moderately enabled (Figure 6). The rest of case studies form another cluster where most perspectives

are moderately to strongly enabled. An equivalent clustering analysis for constraints on perspectives reveals that the case studies *Tatras* and *Coillte*, which report most perspectives being moderately to weakly constrained, cluster together, while the rest of the case studies experience low constraints across all perspectives (*Figure 6* and see also *Figure A1* and *Figure A2* in Annexes).

These patterns reinforce the view that most case studies experience stronger enablers than constraints across most of the perspectives considered, and that constraints are more idiosyncratic than enablers. In addition, the clustering exercise for perspectives enabled reveals that the *Human dimensions* of rewilding (*Social, Policy and Economic* perspectives) form a separate cluster from the *Natural dimensions* (*Ecological and Biophysical, and Climate change adaptation* perspectives, *Figure 6*), suggesting that factors that enable one *Human dimension* also tend to facilitate rewilding across other *Human dimensions*. This also happens in the *Natural dimensions*, apart from *Climate change mitigation*, which seems decoupled from both the *Natural* and the *Human* dimensions, and which is very weakly enabled across half of the case studies irrespective of the other two *Natural dimensions*. In contrast, inspecting the clustering of constraints on perspectives suggests that *Climate change mitigation* and *Climate change adaptation* are usually constrained simultaneously, and that the rest of perspectives do not show strong clustering patterns.

Figure 6. Clustering of case studies according to perspectives enabled (left panel) and perspectives constrained (right panel).

The intensity of the colour illustrates the strength (=median score) for every perspective and case study combination. The vertical dendrogram on top shows hierarchical clustering relationships between case studies, while the horizontal shows clustering relations between perspectives.

Key take home messages from section 2.3

- Most case studies experience stronger enablers than constraints across most of the perspectives considered. *The Social*, and the *Ecological and Biophysical* perspectives are strongly enabled, followed by *Economic*, *Climate change adaptation* and *Policy* perspectives. *Climate change mitigation* is poorly enabled.
- Constraints are more idiosyncratic than enablers and only moderately affect multiple perspectives in two case studies (*Tatras* and *Coillte*). Except *Climate change adaptation* and *Climate change mitigation*, all other perspectives were heterogeneously constrained at some extent in some case studies, but not others.
- Thus, surprisingly, the *Human dimensions* of rewilding (*Social*, *Economic* and *Policy* perspectives) are much more enabled than constrained, highlighting that rewilding projects put strong emphasis in the *Human dimensions*. At the other end is *Climate change mitigation*, which is poorly enabled and constrained, suggesting that, up to now, this aspect of rewilding has received poor attention in rewilding interventions.
- There are shared enablers across the *Human dimensions*: factors that enable one *Human dimension* also tend to facilitate rewilding across other *Human dimensions*.
- There are also shared enablers across some of the *Natural dimensions* (*Ecological and Biophysical*, and *Climate change adaptation* perspectives), but not *Climate change mitigation*, whose enablers are decoupled from the other *Natural dimensions*.
- A set of particularly strong enablers of several perspectives can be identified: these are *Public co-benefits*, the effects of *Regional land use*, *Willingness to experiment*, *Leadership and management*, *Land ownership* and *Congruence with policy*, and, to a lesser extent, *Harvesting opportunities* and *Natural disturbances*. This means that these factors can help to enable rewilding in different projects and across different dimension fronts.
- Only *Leadership and management*, *Conflict with policy* and *Area and upscaling* had weak to moderate leverage as barriers to rewilding (constraints) in several perspectives. These and the impact of the *Local community* and *Harvesting opportunities* can act simultaneously as moderate enablers and constraints in specific dimensions. The rest of constraints are either very weak across perspectives or too idiosyncratic of specific case studies.

2.4 Enablers and constraints across case studies and perspectives

A final generalizing approach involves considering the strength of the different individual enablers and constraints across case studies and across perspectives. Results suggest that the 16 enablers examined differ in their strength (median scores ranging from 2 to 0) but also show large variability in their strengths across case studies and perspectives (*Figure 7*). This again reinforces that there is no “silver bullet” among enablers, and that despite some having stronger positive overall leverage on rewilding than others, their influence might change with perspective and/or case study. On the other hand, examination of results in this and previous sections suggest that a group of four particularly weak enablers across perspectives and case studies can be identified. These are *Nature and connectivity* around the rewilded area, the *Return of iconic species* (except for *Gelderse Poort* and *Baixo Sabor*), *Conflict mitigation* (except for *Barcelona Metropolitan* and *Baixo Sabor*),

and aspects linked to the *Cultural landscape* (except for *Rhurgebiet, Baixo Sabor and Antarr*). The exceptions suggest that these factors might influence a specific case study, but do not have an overall strong effect on enabling rewilding across most of the case studies or perspectives.

Figure 7. Strength of enablers across case studies and perspectives.

Enablers are ordered from larger to lesser strength (top to bottom). The purple text box highlights a group of stronger enablers and the orange a group of weaker enablers. Boxplots show, per enabler, the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points). Enablers are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

None of the 16 constraints considered had a widespread strong leverage on rewilding across case studies and perspectives but all show large variability in their strengths (Figure 8). Again, examination of results in this and previous sections suggest that most constraints (eleven out of the sixteen considered) had particularly weak leverage across perspectives and case studies. These are *Nature and connectivity* around the rewilded area and aspects linked to the *Cultural landscape*, *Operational costs*, *Initial costs*, *Local community* (except for the *Social perspective* at very specific case studies), *Aversion to experiment*, *Regional land use* (except for *Tatras*), *Return of iconic species* (except for *Gelderse Poort*), *Harvesting opportunities* (except for the *Economic perspective* at very specific case studies), *Nature and connectivity* around the rewilding area (except for the *Ecological and Biophysical perspective*), and *Land ownership* (except moderately for *Barcelona Metropolitan* and *Tatras*).

Figure 8. Strength of constraints across case studies and perspectives.

Constraints are ordered from larger to lesser strength (top to bottom). The red dotted text box highlights a group of moderate constraints and the orange a group of weaker constraints. Boxplots show, per constraint, the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points). Constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

Key take home messages from section 2.4

- There is no “silver bullet” among enablers: despite some having stronger positive overall leverage on rewilding than others, their influence might change with perspective and/or case study. However, a set of particularly weak enablers are *Nature and connectivity* around the rewilded area, the *Return of iconic species* (except for *Gelderse Poort* and *Baixo Sabor*), *Conflict mitigation* (except for *Barcelona Metropolitan* and *Baixo Sabor*), and aspects linked to the *Cultural landscape* (except for *Rhurgebiet*, *Baixo Sabor* and *Antarr*).
- Most constraints (eleven out of the sixteen considered) had particularly weak leverage across perspectives and case studies. The strongest constraints were *Natural disasters*, *Leadership management*, *Conflict with policy*, *Wildlife conflicts*, *Natural disturbances*, and *Area and upscaling*.

3. Conclusion

3.1 Enablers and constraints of rewilding across wide gradients

Multiple factors can affect the progress and success of rewilding projects. Our survey of enablers and constraints of the case studies in the wildE project, which represent rewilding projects across a wide European gradient of social, economic, political and environmental contexts, allowed us to identify a diversity of factors affecting rewilding and revealed some a priori surprising patterns across the *Human* and *Natural* dimensions and *Climate-smart* perspectives in rewilding practice.

The survey reveals a high level of heterogeneity amongst case studies and within case studies in the strength of enablers and constraints. This is expected, as case studies represent different archetypes of rewilding that encapsulate different ways of understanding rewilding, emphasizing different processes and from different social, economic and ecological spectrum. Some case studies experience multiple strong enablers (*Barcelona Metropolitan*, *Gelderse Poort*, *Tatras* and *Baixo Sabor*), some others some strong (and shared) enablers (*Antarr* and *Ruhrgebiet*), and some others consistently weak enablers (*Coillte* and *Sveaskog*). However, and perhaps surprisingly, factors enabling rewilding are stronger than those constraining rewilding across case studies, per case study, across perspectives and per perspective. Furthermore, no “silver-bullet” was found across these enablers, as multiple factors contributed to facilitate rewilding in case studies and per perspective. These factors are listed in *Table 5*: as can be seen in the table, 11 of the 16 enablers considered have wide leverage across case studies and perspectives, and further 4 had strong leverage in a particular perspective or case studies. Only the state of *Nature and connectivity* with other natural areas around the rewilded area appeared almost irrelevant as an enabler of rewilding. From an ecological point of view, the ecological quality of the landscape matrix is considered a major factor in the return of wildlife to a certain area, and thus results suggest that landscapes around the case studies do not facilitate the return of wildlife. Indeed, for the *Ecological and biophysical* perspective, this was the strongest constraint.

Factors constraining rewilding were generally idiosyncratic of every case study, apart from *Tatras* and *Coillte* where constraints showed more regular leverage. Despite such general weak to moderate weight of enablers on case studies and perspectives, a “shortlist” of most important constraints can be derived from the results discussed in previous sections (see *Table 5*). *Natural disasters* and *Natural disturbances* posed constraints across several perspectives and in several case studies, highlighting that risks related to natural events like fire, floods, droughts, windstorm and pest outbreaks might represent a burden for rewilding projects. Another group of key factors constraining rewilding relates to return of wildlife and management of the rewilding areas. Here, studies report that leadership and aspects related to management of rewilded areas, the conflicts that rewilding might generate with policy, the problems generated by wildlife conflicts, and at some extent, the return of iconic species (the latter particularly in *Tatras* and *Gelderse Poort*) can slow down rewilding progress. A third group of factors constraining rewilding relates to the limitations posed by the size of the rewilding area and the landscape surrounding the case studies, the dominant regional land uses and state of nature and connectivity with other natural areas around the rewilded area. From an ecological point of view, these have since long been recognized as constraining factors for ecosystem restoration and wildlife conservation.

Important enablers	Important constraints
(Regional) Land use trends	Natural disasters
Public co-benefits	Natural disturbances
Natural disturbances	Leadership and management
Harvesting opportunities	Conflict with policy

Congruence with policy Natural disasters Land ownership Willingness to experiment Area size and upscaling possibilities Leadership and management Initial investment costs Local community involvement and support* (<i>Social perspective</i>) Conflict mitigation strategies* (<i>Barcelona Metropolitan, Baixo Sabor</i>) Cultural significance of the landscape* (<i>Rhurgebiet, Baixo Sabor and Antarr</i>) Return of iconic species to the landscape* (<i>Gelderse Poort and Baixo Sabor</i>)	Human-wildlife conflicts Area size and upscaling possibilities Connectivity and state of nature in the surrounding landscape* (<i>Ecological and Biophysical perspective</i>) (Regional) Land use trends* (<i>Ecological and Biophysical perspective; Tattras and Gelderse Poort</i>) Return of iconic species to the landscape* (<i>Tattras and Gelderse Poort</i>)
Weak enablers	Weak constraints
Connectivity and state of nature in the surrounding landscape* (<i>Rhurgebiet</i>)	Land ownership Harvesting opportunities Aversion to experiment Local community exclusion or opposition Initial investment costs Cultural significance of the landscape Opportunity costs

Table 5. List of important enablers and constraints, and weak enablers and constraints.

When a factors only affected specific perspectives or case studies these are highlighted in brackets. Some enablers and constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

These constraints listed emerge as relatively important across the set of case studies and their very heterogeneous ecological, social, economic and political contexts. Thus, focal attention to minimizing these constraints could be instrumental in facilitating success and progress in a wide range of rewilding interventions. Furthermore, these factors are also listed as important enablers, suggesting that certain aspects of these factors also act as enablers of rewilding interventions. Thus, a potential key strategy would be to find ways to minimize the negative aspects of these factors and maximize their positive aspects.

Another key inference from the results is that some constraints that are commonly assumed to have a negative impact on rewilding show weak leverage or are idiosyncratic to some specific case studies. These include *Land ownership, Harvesting opportunities, Aversion to experiment, Local community exclusion or opposition, Initial investment costs, Cultural significance of the landscape* and *Opportunity costs*. Some of these factors are commonly assumed to pose substantial barriers to rewilding, yet our survey strongly suggests otherwise.

3.2 The *Human vs. Natural* dimensions of rewilding, and *Climate-smart* perspectives of rewilding across wide gradients

Another surprising result from our survey is the realization that the *Human dimensions* of rewilding (*Social, Economic* and *Policy* perspectives) are much more enabled than constrained, highlighting that, despite the heterogeneous and wide social, economic and ecological contexts represented by wildE case studies, rewilding projects already put strong emphasis in the *Human dimensions*. This rejects the widely spread misconception that rewilding (as a nature restoration practice) emphasizes “nature for nature”; instead, our results reveal that rewilding interventions pay great consideration to social and economic aspects. Policy aspects are somehow slightly less enabled than social and economic aspects, perhaps reflecting some of the political and legal constraints that rewilding (and, in general, nature restoration and conservation) experiences. Nevertheless, our results also suggest shared enablers across the *Human dimensions*, highlighting that, at some extent, factors that enable one *Human dimension* also tend to facilitate rewilding across other *Human dimensions*.

This is also the case across the *Ecological and Biophysical*, and *Climate change adaptation* perspectives which also share some enablers. For the *Ecological and Biophysical* perspective this is perhaps not surprising, as the remit of rewilding projects is nature restoration. However, the fact that *Climate change adaptation* is, at some extent, already addressed in many rewilding interventions is encouraging, and highlights that practitioners are already implementing some *Climate-smart* measures in rewilding. However, interestingly, enablers of *Climate change adaptation* were particularly weak in the two case studies involving commercial forestry partners (*Antarr* and *Sveaskog*), which can be interpreted as a sign that *Climate change adaptation* is lagging in (at least some) forestry plantations.

Another key result is that *Climate change mitigation* is poorly enabled or constrained in rewilding projects. This result suggests that, until now, rewilding interventions have paid few attention to the synergies (and trade-offs) that rewilding might pose to mitigate Climate change by e.g. capturing carbon and/or reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Leveraging the potential of different types of rewilding interventions in contributing to mitigate Climate change is precisely one of the key aspects of the wildE project, and one that, in combination with Climate change adaptation, can play a critical role in generating a positive momentum for rewilding across Europe. Our study suggests that despite prevailing views on the potential and the future of rewilding as a mainstream *Climate-smart* restoration practice are rather skeptical, rewilding projects across Europe experience many enablers, leverage the *Human* dimensions as much as the *Natural* dimensions of rewilding, and experience a much more reduced number of idiosyncratic constraints. In the light of these results, the prospects for that positive momentum for *Climate-smart rewilding* can be regarded as quite positive.

4. Annexes

Table A1. Average score of every enabler per case study.

Enablers are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

Constraint	Antarr	Coillte	Ruhrgebiet	Sveaskog	Baixo Sabor	Barcelona Metro	Gelderse Poort	Tatras
Natural disasters	1,500	1,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	1,667	0,000	3,000
Natural disturbances	0,500	1,000	0,000	0,500	1,333	0,000	0,000	1,000
Local community	0,000	0,000	0,500	0,000	0,833	0,000	0,167	1,000
Leadership management	0,000	1,000	0,500	0,167	0,000	3,000	0,000	1,000
Aversion experiment	0,000	1,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	1,667
Cultural landscape	0,000	1,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,500	0,833
Land ownership	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,333	0,000	1,833	0,667	1,333
Region land use	0,000	1,000	0,000	0,333	0,000	0,000	0,500	1,667
Nature connect around	0,000	1,000	1,000	0,500	0,000	0,000	0,500	1,000
Area and upscaling	0,000	1,000	1,000	0,500	0,000	0,000	0,667	1,167
Conflict policy	0,167	1,000	0,000	0,000	1,667	0,000	1,167	1,000
Wildlife conflicts	0,667	1,000	0,000	0,000	2,000	0,000	0,000	1,167
Return iconic sp	0,000	0,833	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	1,333	1,333
Harvesting opport	1,000	0,833	0,000	0,500	0,000	0,000	0,333	1,167
Initial costs	1,000	1,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,333	0,000
Opp costs	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,500	0,000	0,000	0,167	0,500

Table A2. Average score of every constraint per case study.

Constraints are abbreviated (for full name see Table 1).

Enabler	Antarr	Coillte	Ruhrgebiet	Sveaskog	Baixo Sabor	Barcelona Metro	Gelderse Poort	Tatras
Natural disasters	1,500	1,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	2,000	2,500	2,500
Natural disturbances	1,167	1,000	1,167	1,000	0,333	2,000	2,500	3,000
Local community	0,833	1,000	0,833	0,500	1,667	2,333	1,333	1,500
Leadership management	1,667	1,000	1,667	0,500	2,000	2,333	2,500	1,000
Willing experiment	1,667	1,000	2,333	0,000	1,667	2,167	1,667	2,000
Cultural landscape	1,667	1,000	2,333	0,500	2,000	0,000	0,000	0,667
Land ownership	3,000	1,000	2,500	0,500	1,333	1,000	0,667	1,833
Region land use	1,667	1,000	2,500	0,000	2,167	2,333	1,000	2,167
Nature connect around	0,167	1,000	1,333	0,500	0,000	0,000	0,333	1,000
Area and upscaling	1,667	1,000	1,833	0,833	0,000	0,000	1,000	2,167
Congruence policy	1,833	0,000	1,833	0,500	1,833	2,500	2,000	1,333
Conflict mitig	0,333	0,000	0,000	0,500	2,167	2,500	0,833	1,333
Return iconic sp	0,500	0,833	0,000	0,000	1,833	0,000	1,500	1,333
Harvesting opport	1,167	1,000	0,000	0,833	2,167	2,500	2,333	1,000
Initial costs	0,667	1,000	0,000	0,000	2,500	2,333	1,333	3,000
Public cobenefits	2,000	1,000	2,000	0,500	2,833	2,333	1,833	0,500

Figure A1. Strength of perspectives enabled in every case study.

Boxplots show, per perspective, the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points).

Figure A2. Strength of perspectives constrained in every case study.

Boxplots show, per perspective, the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points).

Figure A3. Strength of enablers per perspective.

Boxplots show, per enabler, the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points).

Figure A4. Strength of constraints per perspective.

Boxplots show, per constraint, the median (black vertical line), the interquartile range (box), minimum and maximum values (extremes of the horizontal lines) and potential outliers (points).

Questionnaire 1. Enablers (supplementary file)

Questionnaire 2. Constraints (supplementary file)

Project Partners

wildE is a project researching climate-smart rewilding as a solution to the twin threats of climate change and biodiversity loss.

wildE will test climate-smart rewilding at eight carefully selected sites across Europe. Nature will be allowed to take care of itself, naturally repairing damaged ecosystems and restoring landscapes.

wildE will develop, assess and enhance each approach taken with a broad range of stakeholders to ensure they are economically viable and support both nature and people.

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